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Principles of Paralinguistics in Spoken English

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***Annotation:** The significance of body language in oral communication for foreign language learners in cross-cultural communication is demonstrated by this study. However, the integration of paralinguistics into the classroom has received very little attention in the global context. This work seeks to clarify the fundamentals of paralinguistics while paying particular attention to how foreign language learners employ paralinguistic components in an Uzbek setting.*

***Key words:** paralinguistics, communication, body language, language, non-traditional, communicative competence, sociolinguistic competences.*

To come in

Discussing the function of language in teaching and learning is the goal of educational linguistics, which begins with practical challenges in education¹. While some linguists have studied outside of educational institutions to concentrate on language learning and teaching in non-traditional or informal methods, many educational linguists have addressed the functions and uses of linguistic forms in classroom situations in the literature.² One of the main components of intercultural communicative competence is knowing “how” and “what to say” to someone. The primary goal of foreign language instructors is to push their students to develop discourse, strategic, and sociolinguistic competences, as defined by Canale and Swain³, in addition to the grammatical ability to arrange the SVO. These kinds of communicative skills help language learners stay focused on the language context and their interlocutors' nonverbal clues.

¹ Hornberger, N. H. (2001). Educational Linguistics as a field. Philadelphia, PA: John Benjamins.

² Hult, F. M. (2010). Educational Linguistics: Directions and Prospects for Educational Linguistics. Springer Press.

³ Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. Applied Linguistics 1(1), 1-47.

Educational linguistics's intellectual endeavors are still influenced by the concepts of communicative competence and intercultural communicative competence⁴. Chomsky's distinction between competence and performance—competence being the shared knowledge of an ideal speaker-listener in a completely homogeneous speech community, and performance being the process of applying knowledge to use the language—was the original source of the concept of Linguistic Competence⁵. Chomsky's theory was questioned by Hymes⁶, who claimed that it was too specific to explain language behavior in its whole⁷. He went on to say that social factors had an impact on both internal competence and external performance. Both linguistic and communication competences are necessary for language users in production. Linguistic proficiency is associated with the concepts of comprehending and generating.

According to Kramsch⁸, some competence-related issues, including understanding how to speak and act appropriately in certain circumstances, are almost identical to performance- and capacity-related concerns. In his study on communicative competence, Kramsch⁹ questioned how speakers are regarded and found that “competent” speakers use “subtle semiotic practices that draw on a multiplicity of perceptual clues to make and convey meaning.” Accordingly, symbolic competence is defined as the capacity to shape and alter the context in which speakers acquire and use the language, as well as the proper ability to use language¹⁰.

Since the majority of the senior English Language and Literature students at a Uzbek public university will be working as English teachers in four or five years, they were selected as study participants. The current study has examined and discussed their degree of paralinguistic recognition. The following are the research questions addressed in this study:

Q1: What proxemics and kinesics are employed by EFL university students?

Q2: Does gender make a substantial difference in how the kinesics and proxemics are used?

Q3: Does the application of proxemics and kinesics alter significantly depending on regional differences?

Q4: Is it possible to teach culture as paralinguistics?

The current study is important because it identifies the kinesics and proxemics that Uzbek EFL senior students employ and examines whether there are any differences in these kinesics and proxemics with respect to gender and regional differences. Similarly, it is widely acknowledged that Uzbek English learners struggle to recognize and produce body language because of the disparities between Uzbek and English in terms of kinesics and proxemics. The research participants, who are aspiring English language teachers, also face a number of challenges related to this subject.

Main aim

Due to linguistic and cultural differences, it is very likely that miscommunication will occur during cross-cultural interactions. However, by improving knowledge of individuals and their cultures, the misunderstandings could be prevented. Examining how individuals from various cultural backgrounds

⁴ Hymes, D. (1972). On Communicative Competence. In *Sociolinguistics Selected readings*. Harmondworth, UK: Penguin Books.

⁵ Chomsky, N. (1965). *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

⁶ Hymes, D. (1972). On Communicative Competence. In *Sociolinguistics Selected readings*. Harmondworth, UK: Penguin Books.

⁷ Corbett, J. (2003). *An Intercultural Approach to English Language Teaching*. Great Britain: Cromwell Press

⁸ Kramsch, C. (1993). *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁹ Kramsch, C. (1993). *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

¹⁰ Kramsch, C. (1993). *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

and subcultures communicate with one another is the focus of cross-cultural communication. Understanding culture as a starting point is the fundamental tenet of cross-cultural communication, which enables effective communication. "We find that cultures differ widely from one another in the amount of emotional expression which is permitted" as Klineberg¹¹ notes. Even though these clichés are always a little exaggerated, it's likely that they do, at least in part, fit a recognized cultural pattern¹². Accordingly, culture plays a significant role in determining how people connect with one another in person, including their language usage, nonverbal cues, and communication style¹³.

Cultural differences are assumed in cross-cultural communication theory¹⁴. These differences could act as communication obstacles. People will be more attentive to cultural facts if they are aware of the similarities and contrasts between cultures. This implies that people can see stimuli and react similarly when they share values and understanding from their histories. Culture is a fundamental component that supports the communication process, and communication is deeply ingrained in culture¹⁵. Numerous research have discovered a very acceptable relationship between language and culture. Therefore, it is essential to take into account the obstacles to cross-cultural communication and to view cultural variation as a reflection of communication¹⁶.

In addition to verbal and vocal communication, nonverbal communication is a knowledge system that is especially useful for building positive relationships or interactions in cross-cultural settings (Pennycook, 1985). Kinesics, proxemics, chronemics, and paralanguage are examples of nonverbal codes. In addition to intonation, rhythm, and other prosodic characteristics, verbal communication also includes nonverbal clues conveyed through mood and oral communication style¹⁷.

The study of non-linguistic vocal communication methods is known as paralinguistics. This includes using various vocal qualities, including speaking in a "breathy" or "gravelly" voice, as well as using loudness, intonation, and pace to express specific emotional values. Non-verbal aspects of communication, such the use of kinesics, are also referred to as "paralinguistics." This involves eye contact, facial expressions, and gestures and is referred to as "body language" or "kinesics"¹⁸.

Paralinguistic components are effective meaning-transmitters. Almost everyone considers smiling to be a gesture of welcome or pleasure. Other facial emotions, meanwhile, might not be as prevalent. While raising one's eyebrows to convey surprise or curiosity may be considered a common behavior in one culture, it may be an exaggerated reaction inducement in another. Additional facial expressions that might transmit messages in communication include biting your lip, which indicates some thought or uncertainty; compressing your lips, which indicates decision or obstinacy; clenching your teeth visibly, which indicates wrath; and so forth.

Although people's gestures may be highly culturally specific, they can convey a wide range of meanings. One can observe a few instances in international communication. British English behavior, for example,

¹¹ Klineberg, O. (1964). *The human dimension in interpersonal relations*. New York: Holt, Rine Hart and Winston.

¹² Klineberg, O. (1964). *The human dimension in interpersonal relations*. New York: Holt, Rine Hart and Winston.

¹³ Klopff, D. W., & Park, M. (1982). *Cross-cultural communication: An introduction to the fundamentals*. Seoul: Hanshin Publishing Co.

¹⁴ Spolsky, B., & Hult, F. M. (2008). *The Handbook of Educational Linguistics*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd.

¹⁵ Reagan, T. G. (2009). *Language Matters: Reflections on Educational Linguistics*. Information Age Publishing, Inc.

¹⁶ Hult, F. M. (2010). *Educational Linguistics: Directions and Prospects for Educational Linguistics*. Springer Press.

¹⁷ Birdwhistell, R. L. (1970). *Kinesics and context*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press. G. Brauer (Ed.) *Body and language: Intercultural learning through drama* (pp. 95-112). Westport, CT: Ablex.

¹⁸ Thornbury, S. (2006). *An A-Z of ELT: A Dictionary of Terms and Concepts Used in English Language Teaching*. Oxford, UK: Macmillan Education.

demonstrates the potency of certain gestures. A shoulder shrug might be interpreted as a sign of relaxation. It may also indicate boredom. Waving can be used to say hello and good-bye, however scratching your head can be seen as a sign of confusion. Furthermore, every cultural setting has unique paralinguistic components that demonstrate cultural standards in both their more polite and less polite versions. As part of a society's cultural message transfer, for instance, the use of arms, hands, and fingers can transmit a message.

In the study of nonverbal communication, proxemics is one of the paralinguistic components that represents haptics (touch), kinesics (body movement), vocalics (paralanguage), and chronemics (temporal structure). "The interrelated observations and theories of man's use of space as a specialized elaboration of culture" is the definition of proxemics. The impact of proxemic behavior, which explains how space is used in interpersonal communication, was the main focus of cultural anthropologist¹⁹. According to him, the emphasis on the space term in proxemics stems from how people interact with one another in their day-to-day lives, which also influences the arrangement, structure, and order of all space-based notions that surround them. It may even be present in their homes, structures, equipment, and every arrangement in the cities where they have resided.

In addition to describing the physical distance between speakers, proximity, posture, and echoing can also be employed to convey a variety of signals to the target. For example, the term "closeness" can relate to intimacy and even a threat to many speakers, whereas the term "distance" might reflect adherence to a formal relationship or, in some cases, a lack of interest in the subject. Furthermore, the idea of proximity can vary from person to person and is frequently culturally unique, meaning that something that seems normal to someone in one culture may appear excessively close or far away to someone in another.

Pitch is often used, which can indicate a variety of cross-language communication patterns. First, it explains why high and rising pitch are used to indicate yes-or-no inquiries, whereas low and falling pitch are used to emphasize things like making comments and asking questions. Asking questions might make the individual asking feel reliant on the other person's willingness to provide the information. Once more, the person is confident in their information when they make statements. Frequent usage of pitch also indicates a shift in attitudes like deference, civility, submission, and insecurity.

High and rising pitches indicate all of these attitudes, while low and falling pitches indicate assertiveness, authority, aggression, onfidence, and menace. Furthermore, the purpose of the particular paralinguistic codes is explained by the inclination of people in conversation to employ low tone for phrases that indicate large or related concepts in the target language and high tone for words that indicate tiny or related concepts. The frequency code is linked by Ohala²⁰ and Gussenhoven²¹ to the high pitch as the primary meaning of small vocalizers and secondary meanings like submissive, subordinate, wanting the goodwill of the receiver, etc., and to the low pitch as the primary meaning of large vocalizers and secondary meanings like dominant, aggressive, threatening,

Two aspects of intonational meaning are 1) language-specific and 2) universal-specific, according to Gussenhoven²². Linguistic form-meaning relations are used to study language-specific intonational

¹⁹ Hall, E.T. (1966). *The hidden dimension*. Garden City, NY: Anchor.

²⁰ Ohala, J. J. (1983). Cross-language use of pitch: An ethological view. *Phonetica*, 40, 1-18.

²¹ Gussenhoven, C. (2002). Intonation and interpretation: phonetics and phonology. In B. Bel, & I. Marlien (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Speech Prosody* (pp. 47-57). Aix-en-Provence: Université de Provence.

²² Gussenhoven, C. (2002). Intonation and interpretation: phonetics and phonology. In B. Bel, & I. Marlien (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Speech Prosody* (pp. 47-57). Aix-en-Provence: Université de Provence.

meaning. According to linguistic theory, form-meaning relations are arbitrary and are acquired by language users through communication. The universality found in paralinguistic form-meaning interactions is the second. The phonetic implementation of the phonologically unique pitch contours allows for a general analysis of it.

The term "grammaticalization" refers to the grammaticalization of paralinguistic form-meaning relations, which include paralinguistic codes like a rising contour or high boundary tone that indicate yes-or-no questions and a falling contour or low boundary tone that indicates assertions. Linguistic form-meaning relationships may clash with paralinguistic codes when language structure changes²³. explains this contradiction between form and meaning by linking high pitch and pitch rise to low pitch and pitch fall in listeners' assessments. Therefore, the pitch contour's end point will be the listener's subjective assessment of the form-meaning relationship.

Conclusion.

What the senior English Language and Literature Department students can comprehend from paralinguistics—more especially, kinesics and proxemics in spoken English—has been examined in this study. The findings of an examination of information obtained through the "Paralinguistics in Spoken English" questionnaire indicate that Turkish senior students employ a variety of verbal and nonverbal language in their oral English communication. Language-specific paralinguistics in an EFL context has been demonstrated by the current study. Therefore, more investigation is necessary. From a theoretical perspective, on the one hand, this study directly addresses the two main concerns of EFL research, the developmental challenges.

In summary, the current study has identified the kinesics and proxemics utilized by Uzbek EFL senior students and examined if there was a significant variation in the way Uzbek EFL senior students used these tools with respect to gender and regional differences. In spoken English, paralinguistics is a significant social and cultural cue. According to Demirezen²⁴ and Hult²⁵, it may aid the listener in identifying numerous facets of the speaker and the topic, even if the speech's content is unintelligible.

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²³ Ohala, J. J. (1983). Cross-language use of pitch: An ethological view. *Phonetica*, 40, 1-18.

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